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ПРАВОВОЕ РЕГУЛИРОВАНИЕ ЦИФРОВОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ

**Directions of the transformation of the civil process
in the context of digitalization and pandemic**

**Regulation of blockchain projects based
on distributed ledger technology**

**The transformation of copyright under
the influence of the development of digital technologies**

**The digital economy as the basis
for the transparency of public relations**

**Problems of implementation
of public control in the digital economy**

**Online mediation as one of the alternative
forms settlement of a public law dispute**

Digitalization and public administration

**Transformation of tax legal relations
in the context of digitalization of the economy**

**Legal personality of artificial intelligence in the context
of teaching disciplines in the field of intellectual
property in the context of digitalization**

Legal aspects of digitalization of the forestry industry

Международный
научно-практический
журнал

**ПРАВО И ЦИФРОВАЯ
ЭКОНОМИКА**

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CONTENTS

Foreword by the Rector of Kutafin Moscow State Law University (MSAL) Viktor Blazheev	5
Introductory remarks by the editor-in-chief Maria Egorova	6

Transformation of private legal sciences in the context of digitalization

Branovitsky K.L., Yarkov V.V. Possible directions of transformation of the civil process in the context of digitalization and pandemic: predictive justice	7
Breu S.U. Regulation of blockchain projects based on distributed ledger technology	14
Vakhabava M. Legal Impact Issues Generated by Smart Contracts	22
Kodaneva S.I. The transformation of copyright under the influence of the development of digital technologies	31

Digitalization and public law

Kiryanov A.Yu. Problems of implementation of public control in the digital economy	39
Arzumanova L.L. Online mediation as one of the alternative forms settlement of a public law dispute	45
Gubin A.M. Digitalization and public administration: specificity of interaction and development paths	50
Moshkova D. M. Transformation of tax legal relations in the context of digitalization of the Russian economy	56

Avant-garde Legal Science in the Digital Age: Expert Opinion

Komarova V.V. Political rights of Russian citizens in the digital environment	63
Egorova M.A. Features of determining the legal personality of artificial intelligence in the context of teaching disciplines in the field of intellectual property in the context of digitalization	73
Zhavoronkova N.G., Shpakovsky Yu.G. Legal aspects of digitalization of the forestry industry	77

Young scientists about the future of legal science in the context of digitalization

Burla V.M. Digitalization as a factor of influence on the development of constitutional axiology	84
Vardanyan L.R. Legal aspects of sampling regulation (digital sampling) in the USA and Germany	92

Digital Law in Legal Literature

Review of publications (monographs, commentaries, textbooks, manuals) devoted to the development of digital law ...	96
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Scientific tribune

Review of anniversary events and scientific and practical conferences dedicated to the development of digital law	103
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REGULATION OF BLOCKCHAINS BASED ON DISTRIBUTED LEDGER TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract:

The digital economy and Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) are developing rapidly into our business and private life. The technology enables a way to secure decentralized datasets without involvement of third parties or intermediates in a secure, auditable and incorruptible way. Storing data on worldwide peer-to-peer networks makes these applications difficult to regulate as they are not residing in a specific area of influence of any given regulation or jurisdiction. Blockchain applications based on DLT offer an extensive level of anonymity to their stakeholders. In future artificial intelligence could start to optimize the applications and trigger decisions automatically which will become a major challenge for competition and anti-trust regulators. Based on the Bitcoin technology we will see that there are fair possibilities to regulate the ledgers indirectly through existing legal and regulatory systems. Also, strong self-regulation will play a part to make these technologies widely acceptable. Capacity building has to be emphasized to keep the asymmetry of information between regulators, industry and consumer as small as possible. Some scholars already claim that blockchains have already started to create a supranational economy in which the classical idea of a legal person is obsolete whereas the supranational law is not really designed to address these new developments yet.

Key Words:

Regulation, Distributed Ledger Technology, Blockchain, Cryptocurrencies,

Introduction:

Since the appearance of Distributed Ledger Technology and accordingly Blockchains there is a new field of challenges to regulators and authorities opening up. Most attention in the public and media has been put on the Bitcoin-Blockchain based on the Open Distributed Ledger Technology. Blockchains are basically algorithms with decentralized data storage on a peer-to-peer network lacking a centralized administration. The software for most blockchain applications is open source and keeps the ledger of all transactions ever occurring on public files. If a blockchain is directly administered, it is not an Open Distributed Ledger anymore.

The inherent decentralizing and anonymity aspects of DLT makes it difficult to define an appropriate jurisdiction. In traditional law, and in absence of any agreement stating otherwise, DLT disputes are normally settled by state courts. But state courts mostly do not have the authority and tools to act in this environment. Missing a clearly defined legislative umbrella for transaction with DLT the regulators have to concentrate on the gatekeepers between the Distributed Ledger and the real world. Here they can regulate through compliance regulations or through determining which ledger is recognised within the existing legal and regulatory system. International initiatives for developing international law for facing the new challenges will be necessary for the future.

Another approach is shown in this paper by presenting the softer self-regulations implemented in Switzerland through the Swiss Crypto Valley Association publishing the ICO Code of Conduct for Switzerland in January 2018.

Still, the fact that some researchers state that Bitcoin with its underlying blockchain has already started to create a supranational economy in which the classical idea of a legal person is obsolete¹, this paper aims to start discussing the possible frictions between blockchain applications, their stakeholders and legislative and regulatory authorities.

1 Dima Starodubcev, "Bitcoin created a supranational economy", published March 17, 2016 on [coinfox.info](http://www.coinfox.info/news/persons/5109-dima-starodubcev-bitcoin-created-supranational-economy)

An important challenge for regulators and society is an increasing asymmetry between the blockchain industry, its stakeholders and the legal system and consumer. Today's approach by various governments to implement more and more legal restrictions on the internet will not prove sustainable². DTL and Blockchain technology is definitely a challenge to legislative and regulatory authorities that is asking for massive capacity building and adjustments of existing legal frameworks to give an answer to the challenges of tomorrow.

Short introduction to Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT)

Ledger Technology has been used for a long time even before the digital version of it existed. Maintaining ledgers is a fundamental tool for accounting since the beginning. The technologies to maintain the ledgers might have changed over time but one thing was always inherent - a third party was registering, validating and overlooking each transaction. This was a basis for the validation and trust the involved parties had into this accounting system.

Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT) is now the first form of ledger that is not relying on any third party for verifying and registering transactions. It delegates the maintenance of the ledger and the responsibility to validate it into the hands of all users of the ledger. This creates a decentralized system of a data register that is transparent, reliable, auditable and incorruptible.

Through its dynamic form DLT has much more potential than static paper-based ledgers. As we already know DLT data is not secured and verified at a centralized place which could become a Single Point of Failure. DLT is avoiding the inclusion of any central authority or intermediate to process, validate or authenticate data. Data will only be included in the DTL after consensus of all parties maintaining the system is reached.

2 UNESCO Global Report 2017/2018 "World Trends in Freedom of Expression and Media Development", published 2017 by UNESCO
http://www.unesco.de/fileadmin/medien/Dokumente/Kommunikation/EN_WTR_2017_Executive_Summary_web.pdf

Copyright: [www.krypto-vergleich.de /distributed-ledger-technology/](http://www.krypto-vergleich.de/distributed-ledger-technology/) - Was ist Distributed Ledger Technology und wie funktioniert es; retrieved April 4, 2021

For inclusion into the DLT all new data will be stamped with the date and time and will be referenced with a unique cryptographic signature. All participants of the DLT can at all times access all data and therefore there is a verifiable and auditable history of all information in a dataset available.

A Distributed Ledger is decentralized through its technology. As soon as any administrator has the control over the network it is not decentralized anymore. So DTL is a first step towards Blockchain technology. But it is important to understand that DTL do not necessarily build up blockchains. It can also be used to build other networks that are maintaining decentralized datasets securely.

Still Blockchain is the most prominent application using Distributed Ledger with a very specific technological basis. In blockchains, groups of datasets with cryptographic signatures are linked to each other to build a chain of datasets. One of the best examples for such an Open Distributed Ledger is Bitcoin as the leading Cryptocurrency.

Copyright: <https://tadeix.com/distributed-ledger-technology/>; the Difference Between Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology; retrieved April 4, 2021

The conclusion is that Distributed Ledger Technology and Blockchains are not the same. Blockchain is in any case using DTL but DTL has not to be a blockchain in each case. The potential of DTL in the future is far greater than solely the use of blockchains, going into multiple areas of our business and private life.

Blockchains and it's most prominent application Bitcoin.

We have seen that Blockchains are Distributed Ledgers so basically an algorithm with decentralized data storage, lacking a central administrator, and where the participants know nothing about each other. Best known as the technology behind bitcoin as the leading cryptocurrency. Bitcoin and its underlying blockchain technology were first introduced by Satoshi Nakamoto in his paper “Bitcoin: A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System”³ in 2008.

The whole software for this kind of cryptocurrencies is open source and keeps the ledger of all transactions ever occurring on public files. The records of all transactions are secured on the computers that build this ledger, but not the whole ledger on all but only small blocks with references to other blocks on all these computers worldwide, linked and secured using cryptography. This means, any alteration of any block cannot be done without alternation of all subsequent blocks which makes the system permanent, efficient, incorruptible, and auditable. So, each transaction and its identification is validated by at least three parties involved in maintaining the whole system and “mining” new blocks of information containing data relating to the actual transaction. By solving mathematical problems presented by the system these blocks are added to the existing blockchain, so all members of the system have access to the data. If a transaction is not verifiable with the existing blockchain the new blocks will not be integrated and so the integrity of the system is guaranteed.

3 Nakamoto Satoshi, “A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System”, published in November 2008
<https://bitcoin.org/bitcoin.pdf>

Blockchains have been described as a potential secure and efficient solution for several applications^{4 5 6}. It is also widely expected that blockchains will track integrity and provenance of other special products like pharmaceuticals, diamonds or seafood in future. Blockchain will change the way of exchanging data and the ability to transact globally in various fields, including financial services. Beside the public blockchains, like the one used by bitcoin, there are new applications like consortium blockchains where the consensus process is limited to predefined nodes of the blockchain i.e., participants and members of the consortium. The access to the blockchain can be public or restricted or even hybrid. In a fully private blockchain the write permission is kept by one organisation, but it might be possible to have public reading permission or even that could be restricted to certain stakeholders of the blockchain. In contrast to the public blockchains, consortium or private blockchains can easily change rules and entries in the ledger and even revert processes. But having a central entity controlling the blockchain and being capable of interfering with the algorithm, especially for the challenges discussed in this paper, might solve the problem to define a responsible legal entity and take legal actions against it. This makes a big difference to Open Distributed Ledger Technology where such a legal entity is difficult to define.

Legal Responsibility in an Open Distributed Ledger using Artificial Intelligence

Especially Open Distributed Ledgers that have no administrator with any possibility to interact with the decentralized ledger are creating a new challenge to our law systems. The inherent decentralizing aspects make it difficult to define an appropriate jurisdiction. In traditional law, and in absence of any agreement stating otherwise, disputes regarding legal problems involving DLT are normally settled by state courts. But the inherent structure is creating nearly insoluble problems to such state courts.

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- 4 Robert Plant, “Can Blockchain Fix What Ails Electronic Medical Records?” published on April 27, 2017 in the Wall Street Journal
<https://blogs.wsj.com/experts/2017/04/27/can-blockchain-fix-what-ails-electronic-medical-records/>
 - 5 Nathaniel Popper, Steve Lohr, “Blockchain, A Better Way to Track Pork Chops, Bonds, Bad Peanut Butter?”, published March 4, 2017 in the New York Times
<https://www.nytimes.com/2017/03/04/business/dealbook/blockchain-ibm-bitcoin.html>
 - 6 Rachel Arthur, “From Farm To Finished Garment: Blockchain Is Aiding This Fashion Collection With Transparency”, published May 10, 2017 by Forbes
<https://www.forbes.com/sites/rachelarthur/2017/05/10/garment-blockchain-fashion-transparency/#4975681774f3>

Transactions are conducted completely independently from the physical location of the involved legal entities. Stakeholders can act in various jurisdictions simultaneously in high anonymity with decentralised storage on large peer-to-peer computer networks. For example Bitcoin with its underlying blockchain has already started to create a supranational economy in which the classical idea of a legal person is obsolete⁷ whereas the supranational law is not really designed to address these new developments yet.

As the courts and states have enormous problems to tackle in these new scenarios there are some ideas how to come into a position to be able to regulate the markets beside self-regulation. One opinion on this jurisdictional issue is: “that at a simple level, every transaction potentially comes under the legislative umbrella of wherever the node exists whether in respect of financial services or data protection.”⁸. Whereas the author also states that this means that blockchains would then need to be compliant with a potentially unwieldy number of legal and regulatory regimes.

Given this, the locus of a relevant “act” could be unclear as the transactions may have occurred simultaneously in a few different places, which again makes it nearly impossible to determine the competent jurisdiction. The unsolved questions regarding competence of jurisdictions in these new challenges of the new digital economy will become more and more important in our business and private life.

Whether in a distributed ledger, a blockchain consortium or a private blockchain, a deep cooperation and interaction between stakeholders is necessary to take full advantage of the potential. Blockchains are unified platforms with unified processes to maintain its structures. Attention has to be paid to the fact that all information shared between the stakeholders are only used to help the consortium to achieve legitimate goals and not violate competition laws and regulations. In future artificial intelligence could open a completely new field as blockchains will start to operate independently to optimize prices and profits by using the data stored within the ledger and trigger decisions and actions automatically.

7 Dima Starodubcev, “Bitcoin created a supranational economy”, published March 17, 2016 on coinfox.info <http://www.coinfox.info/news/persons/5109-dima-starodubcev-bitcoin-created-supranational-economy>

8 Gregory Brandman, Samuel Thampapillai, “Blockchain – Considering the Regulatory Horizon”, published July 2016 by University of Oxford, Faculty of Law, Business Law Blog <https://www.law.ox.ac.uk/business-law-blog/blog/2016/07/blockchain—considering-regulatory-horizon>

For state legislation it is difficult to implement regulations that have to be followed in a system that is outside its sphere of influence and action. An autonomous system maintained and managed by the users themselves over which no state organization has any influence and control might, for example, become a major challenge for competition and anti-trust law in future.

Legislative and Regulative Approaches

Within this new digital economy there is no technical necessity for the stakeholders to be attached to any jurisdiction. The high degree of anonymity of stakeholders in an Open Distributed Ledger is extremely challenging for legislation as - for example - we still do not know the real identity behind “Nakamoto Satoshi” who presented the first concept of bitcoin to the public back in 2008.

Our existing legal frameworks are based on the state’s monopoly on violence. If any actor decides not to follow the regulator’s regulation he goes to court. But who can we bring to court in a Open DLT?

As a first step for implementing regulations some states defined some rules for self-regulation like Switzerland through the Swiss Crypto Valley Association publishing the ICO Code of Conduct for Switzerland in January 2018. As an example of soft regulations the Code of Conduct addresses the following points:

A. Business Conduct

Members do their business in a responsible and transparent way, and do not engage in practices which would be potentially or factually damaging to the image and interests of the CVA and the ecosystem. Members adhere at all times to the Codes and, beyond it, to the applicable laws and regulations.

B. Diversity and Inclusion

Members do not discriminate in the work environment based upon race, color, gender, sexual orientation, religion, age, national origin, or disability.

C. Books and Records

Members ensure adequate and truthful operating and financial accounting as well as a proper system to record their business files. Members notify the CVA any changes of their address, email, mobile number, domain name.

D. Property Rights

Members respect property rights of others, such as intellectual property rights, brand names or copyrights associated with any crypto valley related business.

E. Governance and Conflicts of Interests

Members implement in their organizations governance policies to ensure proper operation and control and to avoid (potential) situations of conflict of interest.

F. True and Fair Communication

Members commit to full, accurate, timely and understandable communication. In compliance with their confidentiality obligations, members are encouraged to disclose any form of mismanagement, corruption, incident, illegality, wrongdoing and any other serious infringements of the rules in force at the CVA or of national or local laws, to the CVA Board of Directors.

G. Breaches / Disciplinary Action

Members accept that any breach of the Code can result in disciplinary actions, which, depending upon the nature and severity of the breach, include written warnings, information and/or remediation requests, and – in case of serious breaches – expulsion from the CVA. The Members shall always have the right to be heard and costs shall be allocated to the Member depending on the disciplinary action decided.

H. Transactions

Members shall remunerate transactions on an “arm’s length” basis. Hence, any fees, salaries or “cost-plus” mark-ups shall be comparable with third-party transactions.

Despite the softness of such regulations, it is very difficult to establish a harder regime comparable to traditional regulation of markets. Mainly because the concept of legal entities is nearly impossible to maintain with Open Distributed Ledger Technology. All legal entities

that can be defined as such under traditional law are gatekeepers of the underlying blockchain that exists virtually.

As mentioned before, the potential of Open Distributed Ledger Technology can only be presumed today. To quote Leanne Kemp, CEO of Everledger, from the IBM Institute for Business Value report: “At its core, blockchain is a shared ledger that allows participants in a business network to transact assets where everyone has control but no one person is in control”.⁹ Validated supply chains will be available to the consumers, healthcare data will be managed in blockchain consortia models, and financial trading platforms will be managed through blockchains. Smart contracts will facilitate, execute and enforce agreements through blockchain technology and will guarantee proper fulfilment of the agreement and secure storage of data. This technology will make the use of intermediates and middlemen more and more neglectable.

Further discussing the challenge to regulate Open Distributed Ledger through state authorities we have to answer some questions first. It seems appropriate to start discussion with the most prominent application based in an Open DLT, today still Bitcoin. On-ledger currencies such as Bitcoin are completely different to sovereign currencies, fiat or not. A Bitcoin cannot be exchanged for any commodity as it is not backed by any trusted institution or government. The worth of a Bitcoin is purely a function of the demand in the markets which leads to a significant volatility. For that reason, Bitcoin is traded in the markets more like an asset than a currency.

We should remind us that the main purpose of regulating a currency is to make a currency stable and predictable for international trade. Monetary interventions try to control inflation and to store the value to make a currency a fair medium of exchange. But do we have to ensure the stability of a cryptocurrency? As long as there is reliable market information for consumers we can surely delegate the risks of the volatility to the consumers. It is not a problem for regulators to solve¹⁰.

9 IBM Institute for Business Value, “Forward Together: Three ways blockchain Explorers chart a new direction”, published as Global C-suite Study 19th Edition

<https://www-01.ibm.com/common/ssi/cgi-bin/ssialias?htmlfid=GBE03835USEN>

10 Deloitte. Centre for the Edge, “Bitcoin, Blockchain & Distributed Ledgers; Caught between promise and reality”, published 2016 by Deloitte. Centre for the Edge

<https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/au/Images/infographics/au-deloitte-technology-bitcoin-blockchain-distributed-ledgers-180416.pdf>

We should concentrate on the traditional monetary tasks of Governments and their agencies and remember that the vast majority of distributed ledgers operate inside established regulatory regimes.

For example early in the history of Bitcoin there was concern that anonymity would enable money laundering and fraud easily. These concerns have been proven unfounded.

While the Open Distributed Ledger of Bitcoin itself exists outside of regulatory structures, it must be connected to the real world so for example the market value of a Bitcoin can be realized. These bridges or gatekeepers between the DLT and the real world are today subject to existing regulations and have to adhere to compliance requirements.

Through regulation of these gatekeepers' regulators have a powerful tool to indirectly manage the ledger itself. This is regardless of the ledger's content: be it assets, contracts or entitlements. To enable the transfer of ownership of a physical asset recorded with DLT, the ledger itself has to be recognized by the legal system. Regulation of Open Distributed Ledger can effectively be organized by determining which ledger is recognised by the existing legal and regulatory system.

The coming years will show an enormous development of blockchain technology impacting all aspects of life on a day-to-day basis. One of the main challenge for regulators and society is an increasing asymmetry between the blockchain industry, its stakeholders and the legal system and consumer. Today's approach by various governments to implement more and more legal restrictions on the internet will not prove sustainable¹¹. All regulations and restrictions should consider the specific aspects of Distributed Ledger Technologies and Blockchains and not diminish the potential positive effects of economic growth and innovation.

11 UNESCO Global Report 2017/2018 "World Trends in Freedom of Expression and Media Development", published 2017 by UNESCO
http://www.unesco.de/fileadmin/medien/Dokumente/Kommunikation/EN_WTR_2017_Executive_Summary_web.pdf

Conclusion

Open Distributed Ledger Technology is opening a challenging new field for legislative regulations and law enforcement. The decentralized and autonomous technology and structure of the peer-to-peer network and the complete impossibility of direct intervention by any state institutions poses unseen challenges. Blockchains based on DLT might prove to be agnostic to any jurisdictional rules based on traditional legislative understanding. Blockchain consortia using artificial intelligence will go beyond the market structure as we have it today. Artificial Intelligence combined with a blockchain might well trigger decisions and actions automatically and without interference of any blockchain stakeholders in the future.

Even if Blockchains based on DLT itself might give great concern to regulators we still have to remember that most DLT applications are operating within established regimes. The ones existing outside of regulatory structures can be strongly influenced indirectly through regulating the gatekeepers that connect the DLT with the real world. Then all content of the ledger has sooner or later to be transferred into the real world. At this stage regulations can be effective.

Still capacity building has to be emphasized to keep the asymmetry of information between regulators, industry and consumers as small as possible. Self-regulation by the market players will be necessary to support. International coordination of regulations and addressing the problem of missing legislative umbrellas for decentralized databases can only be addressed globally.

References:

1. Nakamoto Satoshi, "A Peer-to-Peer Electronic Cash System", published in November 2008
<https://bitcoin.org/bitcoin.pdf>
2. Gregory Brandman, Samuel Thampapillai, "Blockchain – Considering the Regulatory Horizon", published July 2016 by University of Oxford, Faculty of Law, Business Law Blog
<https://www.law.ox.ac.uk/business-law-blog/blog/2016/07/blockchain---considering-regulatory-horizon>
3. Dima Starodubcev, "Bitcoin created a supranational economy", published March 17, 2016 by coinfox.info
<http://www.coinfox.info/news/persons/5109-dima-starodubcev-bitcoin-created-supranational-economy>

4. Sergii Shcherbak, “How Should Bitcoin Be Regulated?”, published Spring/Summer 2014, Volume 7, Issue 1, in European Journal of Legal Studies
<http://www.ejls.eu/15/183UK.pdf>
5. Ajinkya M. Tulpule, “Enforcement and Compliance In A Blockchain(ed) World” published January 2017 by CPI – Competition Policy International
<https://www.competitionpolicyinternational.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/CPI-Tulpule.pdf>
6. Gregory Brandman, Samuel Thampapillai, “Blockchain – Considering the Regulatory Horizon”, published July 2016 by University of Oxford, Faculty of Law, Business Law Blog
<https://www.law.ox.ac.uk/business-law-blog/blog/2016/07/blockchain---considering-regulatory-horizon>
7. Crypto Valley Association, “Mission and Policy Framework/General Code of Conduct”, published January 2018
<https://cryptovalley.swiss/codeofconduct/>
8. Marco Iansiti, Karim R. Lakhani, “The Truth About Blockchain”, published January/February 2017 Issue Harvard Business Review
<https://hbr.org/2017/01/the-truth-about-blockchain>
9. IBM Institute for Business Value, “Forward Together: Three ways blockchain Explorers chart a new direction”, published as Global C-suite Study 19th Edition
<https://www-01.ibm.com/common/ssi/cgi-bin/ssialias?htmlfid=GBE03835USEN>
10. UNESCO Global Report 2017/2018 “World Trends in Freedom of Expression and Media Development”, published 2017 by UNESCO
http://www.unesco.de/fileadmin/medien/Dokumente/Kommunikation/EN_WTR_2017_Executive_Summary_web.pdf
11. Deloitte. Centre for the Edge, “Bitcoin, Blockchain & Distributed Ledgers; Caught between promise and reality”, published 2016 by Deloitte. Centre for the Edge
<https://www2.deloitte.com/content/dam/Deloitte/au/Images/infographics/au-deloitte-technology-bitcoin-blockchain-distributed-ledgers-180416.pdf>
12. Tradeix.com “The Difference between Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology”. published 2018 by tradeix.com
<https://tradeix.com/distributed-ledger-technology/>
13. Krypto-Vergleich.de “Distributed Ledger Technology: Was ist DLT und wie funktioniert es»; published 2019 by Krypto-vergleich.de
<https://krypto-vergleich.de/distributed-ledger-technology/>
14. Roger Wattenhofer, “Distributed Ledger Technology: The Science of the Blockchain», published March 2017 by CreateSpace Independent Publishing Platform;
ISBN: 978-1-5442-3210-2
15. Robert M. Townsend, “Distributed Ledger: Design and Regulation of Financial Infrastructure and Payment Systems”, published October 2020 by The MIT Press;
ISBN: 978-0-2625-3987-6
16. Asian Development Bank, “Distributed Ledger Technology and Digital Assets – Policy and Regulatory Challenges in Asia”, published June 201 by Asian Development Bank;
ISBN: 978-9-2926-1646-5
17. KJ Arora, “Blockchain Handbook: Essentials of Blockchain Technology and Cryptocurrency», published April 2019 by Independently published;
ISBN: 978-1-0964-1921-1